

STUDY OF GARBHAVRUDDHI WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SHASHTI MAASA.

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ABSTRACT

Acharya Sushruta in his Shareera Sthan explained detailly and scientifically about the Garbha formation, Garbha Sambhavam Samagri as Rutu (the catamanial period), Kshetra (the healthy womb), Ambu (the nutrients fluid of healthy mother) and Beeja (healthy gametes), Matrujadi (matruja, pitruja, Atmaja, Rasaja, Satvaja and satmyaja) Shadbhavas necessary for formation of Garbha, role of Panchamahabhuta in the growth and development of Garbha, Masanumasika Garbha Vruddhi, Rutumati, Sadhyograhita Garbhini, Garbhini Laxanas, Garbhini Paricharya, Sutika Parichaya etc.

KEYWORDS: Garbha, Panchamahabhuta, Shashti Masa, Cognition, Growth and development.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- * Panchmahabhuta role in Garbha Vruddhi.
- * Shashti Masa Garbha Vruddhi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of data

The literary and conceptual study will be done by collecting the data from all Brihatrayees, Laghutrayees and other classical texts and modern books, including journals, paper presentations, previous work done are compiled and analysed.

Method of collection of data

For literary and conceptual study the data will be collected from the classical and modern text books, National and International Journals, Magazines, Seminars, Conferences, Internet material, Previous work done, Presented papers etc. and will be analyzed scientifically to fulfill the objectives.

INTRODUCTION

Shuddha Beeja like healthy Shukra and healthy aartava when meet in the Garbhashya during Rutukala in association with Manas and Atma the Garbha is formed.[1charak] The combination of semen and ovum in the womb, properly amalgated together along with Prakruti and its Vikruti (primordial substance) Jeeva and Matrujadi Shadbhavas is called as the Garbha.^[2]

Fertilization is the union of male and female gametes to be very specific union of male and female pronuclei.it occurs in the ampullary part of the fallopian tube and implanted in the endometrium layer of uterus.^[3]

Need For the study

Role of Panchamahabhuta in Garbha.

The Panchamahabhuta are responsible for the growth and development of garbha along with Matrujadi Shadbhavas as Vayu Mahabhuta divides dosha, dhatu, mala Anga and Pratyanga and also monitors the mind and its activities. Agni Mahabhuta is responsible for all the metabolic activities hence leads to transformation leading to ultimate state of humanbody.

Prithvi Mahabhut does consolidation, gives shape to the embryo and is responsible for all the hard structures and integrity of the body.

Aap Mahabhuta confluence the foetal tissue by nourishing oja etc dhatus and moistening the dryness created by Vayu and Agni Mahabhuta. Akash Mahabhuta helps in development and growth i e increase in size by providing space.^[4]

Masanumasika Garbha Vruddhi

Acharya Sushruta explain monthwise development of Garbha in specific manner. Acharya Sushruta opines, that the Garbha is in Kalala stage in the first month. In the second month it is metabolized under the influence of Sheeta, Ushma and Anila and thus complex of Panchamahabhuta becomes solidified. In the third month foetus grows and five protrusions

appear, one for each limb and fifth for the head region, and the differentiation of organs and parts takes place in minute form.^[5]

In the fourth month Acharya describes that differentiation of organs and structures become more prominent, foetal heart is apparent and mother is called as Dauhradini.^[6]

In the fifth month of garbha's growth and development Acharya says Mana is manifested means enlightened with cognition. In sixth month Buddhi evolves i.e. cognition establishes. In the seventh month differentiation of individual structures and organs becomes more prominent. In the eighth month state of Ojas is unstable and in any of ninth, tenth, eleventh and twelfth month delivery of child may takes place.^[7]

In the specific Shashti Masa(sixth month) of growth and development of Garbha Acharya Charak opines that during this month Bala (strength), Varna (colour & complexion) get nourishment prominently.^[8]and Acharya Kashyap opines same, where as Acharya Sushruta opines about the evolution of Buddhi.^[9] In the context of Garbhini Pathya, in the first .second and third month Madhura(sweet) Sheeta (cold)And Drava (liquid) and in the fourth month cooked rice with curd, in fifth month cooked Shasti rice with milk, nd Sixth month onwards administration of Ghrita (ghee) is advised.^[10]

As the sixth month comes under second trimester according to modern view during the end of first trimester and beginning of second trimester fetal neurons begin to develop dendrites which develops synaptic connections with neighbouring neurons to form vast neural network, and millions of synaptic connections develop during this period of development. Along with this an innate intelligence begins to form the architecture of brain, supports function of brain, mind and consciousness.^[11]

DISCUSSION

In modern, growth and development is the actual change in the cells of body similarly foetus development also. Here we can say, the foetal development ie increase in the cell number done by Panchmahabhutas only as a cell also contains Panchmahabhutas like cell consisting intercellular fluid etc can compare with Jala, Mitochondria which is known as power house of cell is the attribute of Agni, specific shape and structure of cell is gift of Prithvi, as every cell needs oxygen for live ness ie. respiration of each cell is barely Vayu and the cellular space is Akash entity.

When we analyse the above Panchmahabhutas role in formation and development of Garbha we can say in the modern embryology also replicated the same as.

Vayurvibhajati

Vayu mahabhuta divide the fertilised secondary ovum produces several cells from this unit. Thus the process cell division begins from Vayu mahabhuta and creates further movement to embryo for implantation.

Tejaenampachati

Agni mahabhuta helps metabolism, transformation etc. process. During embryo formation when sperm enters into secondary ovum, the acrosomal enzymes like hyaluronidase, more penetrating enzymes does the zonal reaction and gets entry and fertilises the ovum. This zonal enzymatic reaction is due to Agni mahabhuta. Further on the 7th day of fertilisation zona pellucida enzymes reacts with endometrium and the process of implantation also done by agni mahabhuta.

Apah kledyanti

Jala Mahabhuta not merely water, along with the water present in body, body fluids like extra cellular fluid, csf, plasma etc also jala mahabhuta entity. Up to formation of placenta the Garbha gets nourishment by upsveda and upsneha which is jala bhuta predominance. After formation of apara through nabhi naadi rakta dhatu which is jala mahabhuta predominant nourishes the foetus. To give cushioning protection the foetus develops in amniotic fluid which is also the attribute of jala mahabhuta.

Prithvisamhanti

Prithvi mahabhuta maintain integrity ie. samhanan and compactness of cells during cell division. This mahabhuta gives structure, shape, weight to the foetus.

Akashamvividhayati

Akasha mahabhuta provides Vivardhana of the Garbha ie. multidimensional development of the cells in foetus along with porousness in it. with porousness of different cells. In modern, growth and development is the actual change in the cells of body similarly foetus development also. Here we can say, the foetal development ie increase in the cell number done by Panchmahabhutas only as a cell also contains Panchmahabhutas like cell consisting intercellular fluid etc can compare with Jala, Mitochondria which is known as power house of

cell is the attribute of Agni, specific shape and structure of cell is gift of Prithvi, as every cell needs oxygen for live ness ie. respiration of each cell is barely Vayu and the cellular space is Akash entity.

During the sixth month as Acharya Sushruta explained about the Buddhi establishment, in the second trimester fetal brain undergoes many changes related with sensory processing, cognition and consciousness development. Particularly in sixth month nerves and tracts related with the conscious, thinking capacity etc develops. Thalamo-cortical connections i.e. axons bring the connection between thalamus and cerebral cortex building the brain relay station, advanced sensory perception etc. hence increasing the cortical surface area by increasing in sulci and gyri on the cortex.

CONCLUSION

Acharya Sushruta defined Garbha is formed by combination of Shuddha Shukra and Shuddha Aartva along with Atma, Prakruti and its Vikaras. Panchamahabhuta plays an important role in growth and development of Garbha. Acharya mentioned in the sixth month Buddhi evolves by observing pathya during sixth month of Garbhini and contemporary science opinions in the sixth month growth and development of foetus, Acharya Sushruta opinion of Buddhi establishment in the six month is Appreciable.

REFERENCE

1. Sharma R.K, Dash Bhagwan, Caraka Samhita, Shareera Sthan, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Reprint, 2015; 388.
2. Shastri Kaviraj Dr. Ambikadatta, Sushruta Samhita, Shareera Sthan Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Samsthan, Reprint, 2024; 54.
3. Singh Vishram, Textbook of clinical embryology, second edition, Newdelhi: Elsevier, Reprint, 2018; 39.
4. Shastri Kaviraj Dr. Ambikadatta, Sushruta Samhita, Shareera Sthan, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Samsthan, Reprint, 2024; 55.
5. Shastri Kaviraj Dr. Ambikadatta, Sushruta Samhita, Shareera Sthan, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Samsthan, Reprint, 2024; 31.
6. Shastri Kaviraj Dr. Ambikadatta, Sushruta Samhita, Shareera Sthan, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Samsthan, Reprint, 2024; 31.
7. Shastri Kaviraj Dr. Ambikadatta, Sushruta Samhita, Shareera Sthan, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Samsthan, Reprint, 2024; 33.

8. Sharma R.K, Dash Bhagwan, Caraka Samhita, Shareera Sthan, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Reprint, 2015; 398.
9. Shastri Kaviraj Dr. Ambikadatta, Sushruta Samhita, Shareera Sthan, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Samsthan, Reprint, 2024; 33-34.
10. Shastri Kaviraj Dr. Ambikadatta, Sushruta Samhita, Shareera Sthan, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Samsthan, Reprint, 2024; 98-99.
11. Usha V.N.K, Prasuti Tantra, Vol-1, Delhi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan, Reprint, 2015; 203.